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Spectral characterization and comparison of EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD radiochromic films

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Spectral characterization and comparison of EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD radiochromic films

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E-mail: stevan.pecic@ff.bg.ac.rs**Keywords:** EBT3, EBT4, EBT-XD, radiochromic film, absorption spectroscopySupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)**Abstract**

This study analyzed the spectral response of EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD radiochromic films using absorption spectroscopy. The primary focus was on characterizing the evolution of spectral signatures across a range of absorbed doses, thereby elucidating the unique dose-dependent response profiles of each film type. Ten samples of each film type were subjected to open field irradiation within their designated dose ranges (1–20 Gy for EBT3 and EBT4, 1–50 Gy for EBT-XD). The corresponding absorption spectra were recorded and studied via decomposition and parameterization of dose-dependent spectral features. Lorentzian profiles were employed for spectral decomposition. Each film type displayed unique spectral signatures with distinct absorption peaks: nine for EBT3, eleven for EBT4, and twelve constituent profiles for EBT-XD. Notably, the EBT4 film demonstrated a slight difference in the blue part of the absorption spectrum and a change in the response, relative to its EBT3 predecessor. Orientation dependence of the film spectra was most pronounced for the EBT3 film type, followed by a declining trend across EBT4 and EBT-XD films. Absorption spectroscopy portrayed distinct spectral fingerprints of the studied film types, aiding the selection of the most suitable film for specific applications.

1. Introduction

Radiochromic films have become indispensable tools in medical radiation dosimetry due to their unique properties and versatile use. Within a brief timeframe, radiochromic films, renowned for their self-developing nature and superior spatial resolution have substantially streamlined and improved quality assurance and commissioning procedures in medical physics. The ability to record radiation dose by undergoing a color change upon radiation exposure has made radiochromic films particularly valuable for radiation oncology applications (Niroomand-Rad *et al* 1998). Radiochromic films have evolved significantly over the years, with continuous advancements aimed at improving their accuracy and usability. Ashland Inc.'s renowned external beam therapy (EBT) series of radiochromic films, including its subsequent EBT2, EBT3, and EBT-XD iterations, has shown steady improvements in spectral response, energy (in)dependence, and extended dynamic range, catering to diverse clinical applications (Reinhardt *et al* 2012). EBT-XD model, introduced in 2015, has a composition similar to EBT3 but with a smaller crystal size in the active medium, which results in lower sensitivity, suitable for measurement of higher doses (Niroomand-Rad *et al* 2020). Recently, the EBT4 film was introduced to improve the performance of the well-established EBT3 model (Chan *et al* 2023, Palmer *et al* 2023). AAPM Task Group 235 report (Niroomand-Rad *et al* 2020) provides a detailed guide on the characteristics, usage, and applications of the current radiochromic film models.

Absorption spectroscopy is essential in understanding how radiochromic films respond to ionizing radiation. By examining the spectral properties of these films, researchers can gain valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms of color change, as well as the stability and reproducibility of film responses (Butson, Cheung and Yu 2005, Devic *et al* 2007, 2010). Spectroscopic techniques facilitate the exploration of the film absorption spectra, enabling the identification of characteristic peaks and wavelengths associated with radiation-induced color changes. The resulting spectroscopic data can be used to identify absorption bands suitable for constructing calibration curves, which are necessary for converting optical changes into dose values.

Using a synergy of approaches to radiochromic film absorption spectroscopy established in the literature, this study compared the three frequently used radiochromic films, focusing on their spectral characteristics. The objective was to use absorption spectroscopy to compare the dose response of EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD radiochromic films. Insights into the unique spectral characteristics of these film types can aid the selection of the most suitable film for specific dosimetry applications. Lorentzian decomposition was used to identify and study peaks for each film type. Moreover, a novel method for characterizing orientation dependence effects, based on spectral differences, was introduced to facilitate the parameterization of overall response variations. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first comparative study of absorption spectra in the literature. This approach introduces a novel method for characterizing radiochromic films. Furthermore, we have undertaken the pioneering task of evaluating and discussing the orientation-dependent variations in the spectra.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Irradiation

Two sheets of three film types: EBT3 (LOT 03022105), EBT4 (LOT 04072302), and EBT-XD (LOT 02232302) were used in the study. Each sheet was cut into eight strips measuring 2.54 cm × 20.32 cm (1'' × 8''), resulting in a total of 16 strips. A random selection of nine strips from each film type was subsequently irradiated using Varian TrueBeam™ (Varian Medical Systems, Palo Alto, CA, USA) linear accelerator. Each film strip was placed at the center of a solid water RW3 Slab Phantom™ (PTW, Freiburg, Germany) at a 100 cm SSD and 10 cm depth and irradiated with a 6 MV photon beam utilizing a 15 cm × 15 cm open field. The photon fields were designed to deliver doses of 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10, 15, 20 Gy for EBT3 and EBT4 film strips, and 1, 3, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40, 50 Gy for EBT-XD ones. Before irradiation, the output of the linac was verified using a daily constancy check procedure. Lastly, the unexposed control strips for each film type were used for the background baseline signal.

2.2. Spectroscopy

The absorption spectrometry was performed using an Agilent Cary 60™ UV–Vis spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA), within the wavelength range of 400 nm to 700 nm. The absorption spectra were recorded 48 hours post-irradiation to minimize the influence of post-irradiation polymerization. Before spectrum measurement, adjustments for baseline and zero reference points were made on the spectrometer. The spectrometer settings were configured at a resolution of 1 nm and a scanning speed of 1 nm s⁻¹.

The absorbance *Abs* is defined as the logarithm (base 10) of the ratio between incident light intensity I_0 and transmitted light intensity I :

$$Abs = \log_{10} \left(\frac{I_0}{I} \right). \quad (1)$$

To isolate spectral changes induced by radiation, the film spectra were analyzed by subtracting the unirradiated control spectrum. This step resulted in the net spectra, which highlight the radiation-induced spectrum changes. The net absorbance *net Abs* is defined as the difference between the absorbance of an irradiated film $A(D)$ and the absorbance of an unirradiated control film $A(0)$:

$$net\ Abs = A(D) - A(0). \quad (2)$$

The instrument's photometric uncertainty of 0.006 Abs was obtained from the annual calibration certificate. Additional sources of uncertainty may include photometric repeatability, temperature variations, film positioning reproducibility, and background subtraction uncertainty. The vendor's 1.5 nm spectral bandwidth specification of the instrument was rounded to 2 nm and assigned as the measurement uncertainty for peak position determination.

2.3. Spectrum decomposition

Lorentzian decomposition, a powerful technique for analysis of radiochromic film absorption spectrum, was first reported by Devic *et al* (2007). In this study, three different films were subjected to spectrum decomposition analysis to identify and compare the unique spectral components present in each film's spectrum.

The following equation describes the decomposition of the recorded spectrum into n Lorentzian profiles:

$$Abs_{\text{fit}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{2I_i}{\pi} \frac{\omega_i}{4(x - x_{ci})^2 + \omega_i^2} \quad (3)$$

where Abs_{fit} denotes the measured absorbance spectrum decomposed into n profiles, I_i represents the profile area—integral below the profile, x and x_{ci} represent the wavelength and central wavelength, respectively, and ω_i stands for the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of i th Lorentzian profile component. To determine the optimal-fit parameters I_i, x_{ci}, ω_i for $i = 1, \dots, n$ Lorentzian profiles, spectral fitting was conducted by minimizing the subsequent expression:

$$\sum_{j=1}^m \left(Abs_{\text{exp}}(x_j) - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{2I_i}{\pi} \frac{\omega_i}{4(x_j - x_{ci})^2 + \omega_i^2} \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where j is indexing the wavelength x_j . In this expression, the sum $\sum Abs_{\text{exp}}(x_j)$ signifies the spectrum obtained through spectrophotometer measurement, while the subtracted sum corresponds to the Lorentzian-composed spectrum. The number of peaks is adjusted to minimize χ^2 of the resulting fit. Each peak is added one at a time until an acceptable fit is achieved. The number of peaks was adjusted to minimize χ^2 of the resulting fit. Peaks were added sequentially until an acceptable fit was achieved. The optimal number of peaks was determined by minimizing the χ^2 value to a point where further additions resulted in a negligible change, typically on the order of 10^{-6} . Dose dependent peak positions were additionally investigated, with mean peak positions calculated as:

$$x_c = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n_D} x_{ci}}{n_D} \quad (5)$$

where n_D represents the total number of measured dose values.

2.4. Polarization-induced orientation dependence

As noted in the study by Butson *et al* (2003), radiochromic films demonstrate a measurable sensitivity to the polarization state of the light source employed for readout. This effect correlates with the film's orientation relative to its center. The underlying mechanism for this behavior is attributed to the inherent properties of the film's active medium, which induces light polarization during the readout process. This effect becomes evident when measuring the film's absorption spectrum, where the film strip positioned in portrait and landscape orientations produces distinct spectra. The polarization effect was demonstrated for each film type by recording spectra for each film stripe in both landscape and portrait orientations of the same film side, that is, by rotating the films 90 degrees. Two cardinal film orientations can be differentiated by visually comparing their absorption spectra. However, the absolute change in absorption for the measured wavelength range was numerically determined by subtracting absorption spectra obtained for two orthogonal film orientations:

$$\Delta_p(\lambda) = Abs^0(\lambda) - Abs^{90}(\lambda). \quad (6)$$

Here, $\Delta_p(\lambda)$ represents the wavelength-dependent differential absorbance between the two orientations for a given dose level at a discrete wavelength within the spectrum. A comprehensive assessment of the film's orientation sensitivity across the entire spectrum, i.e. the overall relative response change induced by polarization was calculated by summing the squares of the absorbance differences at each wavelength:

$$\sigma = \sum_{\lambda} \Delta_p^2(\lambda). \quad (7)$$

The square metric ensured that both positive and negative absorbance differences were incorporated into the calculation without being offset by one another. The scalar quantity σ , expressed in arbitrary units, quantifies the degree of orientation sensitivity for a given film model. It explicitly demonstrates the wavelength-dependent nature of the polarization effect. Notably, σ is a parameter primarily employed for

comparative analysis of film types. The measurement of orientation-dependent spectral change is not intended to provide precise absorption values at each wavelength but rather to offer an estimate that facilitates comparisons between different film types.

3. Results

The evolution of spectral profiles as a function of absorbed dose for raw and net spectra of EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD films is presented in figure 1. Figures 1(a), (c), and (e) illustrate the raw spectra, while figures 1(b), (d), and (f) display the net spectra for EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD films, respectively.

The absorbance measurement saturation was noticeable in the primary peak, around 15 Gy for EBT3 and EBT4 films, and around 30 Gy for EBT-XD. Spectra from films irradiated with doses near saturation were excluded from the analysis. In addition, the shapes of the primary peak near saturation are shown in the appendix in figure 7.

Figures 2(a), (b), and (c) show a comparison of the net absorption spectra for EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD films irradiated with 1, 3 and 10 Gy, respectively. In the region of the two most prominent peaks, each film type exhibits a similar response. However, differences are visible in the blue part of the spectrum (400–500 nm), where EBT4 and EBT-XD show additional peaks.

The Lorentzian decomposition analysis for films irradiated with 10 Gy is depicted in figure 3. Figures 3(a), (b), and (c) illustrate the Lorentzian decomposition for EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD films, respectively. The optimal number of peaks was determined by minimizing the χ^2 parameter for decompositions with a variable number of peaks (Thorne 1988). This process resulted in 9 peaks for EBT3, 11 peaks for EBT4, and 12 peaks for EBT-XD.

The mean positions of peaks for three film types EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD, are presented in figure 4. In addition, the numerical values (in nm) for the mean peak positions are presented in table 1.

The polarization-induced orientation dependence of the absorption spectrum is presented in figure 5, for the films irradiated with 3 Gy dose level. Figure 5(a) shows the spectrum changes when films are scanned in portrait (0-degree) versus landscape (90-degree) orientation, i.e. for a 90-degree rotation of the film before the readout, with respect to the initial (0-degree) orientation. This phenomenon is further clarified in figure 5(b), where the net difference is shown. As calculated by equation (7), the overall change in response due to polarization, represented by the sum of the squared absorbance differences at each wavelength, was $\sigma = 2.76, 0.62,$ and 0.23 for EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD films, respectively.

The total absorbance difference σ induced by orientation change, as a function of radiation dose, is depicted in figure 6 for each film type.

4. Discussion

Previous EBT film models have been characterized by both phenomenological and mechanistic models to describe their absorption spectra (Moral *et al* 2009, Callens *et al* 2016, 2017, Darafsheh *et al* 2019, León-Marroquín *et al* 2019, Rodríguez and Martínez 2019, Pecić *et al* 2024). The crystal structure of the active medium, composed of diverse chemical elements, provides a foundation for this approach. Given its widespread use in practice, the EBT3 model served as a reference for comparison with the EBT4 and EBTXD models. A historical analysis of spectral composition with discontinued EBT and EBT2 models (Devic *et al* 2007, 2010) identified an additional absorption peak in the EBT3 spectrum. This phenomenon is likely attributed to a modification in film configuration, specifically the substitution of clear polyester with matte polyester as the substrate (Niroomand-Rad *et al* 2020).

In comparison to EBT3, EBT4 exhibits an additional absorption peak in the 400–450 nm range, indicating a notable enhancement in blue channel sensitivity. Although the spectral response of EBT4 at 635 nm was comparable to EBT3, it demonstrated an approximately 20% decrease in responsiveness to green and blue wavelengths. This difference suggests that the new EBT4 film may encompass a higher proportion of the red polymer component, as proposed by Rodríguez *et al* regarding film polymer color phases (Rodríguez and Martínez 2019). Guan *et al* (2023) similarly reported an overall increase in signal-to-noise ratio for EBT4 compared to EBT3 films. Furthermore, the two additional peaks, centered at 401 and 429 nm within the blue part of the spectrum, influence lower dose measurements. However, when using the blue channel for readout, an absolute absorbance difference of less than 0.1 arbitrary units is anticipated. The EBT-XD film incorporates three additional Lorentzian functions in comparison to EBT3, resulting in a total of twelve absorption peaks. These peaks are positioned at 409 nm, 431 nm, and 486 nm, suggesting a slightly different behavior of EBT-XD in the blue channel. As with EBT4, this may affect lower dose measurements

for EBT-XD films, where the contribution of the additional peaks was observed. It is worth noting that there exists a distinguishable gap between the 583 nm and 635 nm absorption bands for all film types, as illustrated in figure 5. In addition to film type differentiation, it is important to note that spectral absorption may vary between different film batches, due to manufacturing processes, and between different acquisition instruments due to changes in source/detector configuration. While we hypothesize that the instrument's influence is relatively small when properly calibrated, it still contributes to the overall measurement uncertainty. Specifically, the spectrophotometer's specifications from the annual calibration certificate and datasheet should be taken into consideration for precise measurements.

(a) 1 Gy dose level

(b) 3 Gy dose level

(c) 10 Gy dose level

Figure 2. Comparison of the net absorption spectra for different radiochromic film types irradiated with (a) 1 Gy, (b) 3 Gy, and (c) 10 Gy.

Previous studies reported an orientation-dependent signal change when using flat-bed scanners (Battum *et al* 2015, Schoenfeld *et al* 2016). These investigations emphasize the importance of maintaining a consistent film orientation during multiple scans to avoid significant errors (Niroomand-Rad *et al* 2020). A study by Khachonkham *et al* (2018) reported pixel value differences of 4.6% and 7.7% for EBT-XD and EBT3 films, respectively. More recently, a study by Miura *et al* (2023) observed optical density differences of 6.8% and

3.9% between the two cardinal scanning orientations for EBT3 and EBT4 films, respectively, at a dose of 2 Gy. The orientation-dependent spectral behavior observed in this study aligns with previous research, providing a comprehensive overview of all three film types within a single analysis. The EBT3 film model exhibited the most pronounced orientation dependence, while EBT4 and EBT-XD demonstrated significantly less pronounced effects. EBT4 films exhibited a substantially reduced overall relative response to orientation compared to EBT3 films, decreasing by over 75% (from 2.76 to 0.62). EBT-XD films were even less sensitive

Figure 4. Mean peak positions for EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD films. The exact numerical values for each position are given in table 1.

to polarization effects, with their overall relative response decreasing by over 90% (from 2.76 to 0.23) compared to the EBT3 baseline. The observed trend of orientation-dependent behavior with absorbed dose, presented in figure 6, was somewhat anticipated; The rod-like morphology of the grown polymer, responsible for light polarization, directly correlates with the concentration of polymer chains present in the active medium. As the film absorbs radiation, the polymeric structure expands, resulting in an intensified manifestation of light polarization behavior. In general, the declining trend in orientation sensitivity for EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD, previously documented by other researchers, is corroborated by figure 6. While the EBT-XD model is rated for doses up to 40 Gy, we hypothesize that the trend visible in figure 6 will persist at higher dose levels. Future investigations could involve quantifying the precise orientation angle changes induced by the film, which may be valuable in the development of a laser densitometer, a device utilizing inherently polarized light.

To a large extent, the goodness of fit is predetermined by the choice of the appropriate decomposition model. Adhering to established practices for identifying absorption bands in crystalline structures (Thorne 1988), all spectra were decomposed into Lorentzian profiles. The suspected presence of instrumental broadening in the primary peak centered at 635 nm suggests the use of a Voigt profile, a convolution of Gaussian and Lorentzian profiles. This approach, however, might not be consistent with the remaining spectral features. The determination of the precise number of peaks in the absorption spectrum is subject to debate, as it depends on the analytical model employed and the minimization metric utilized. While the current analysis identified a specific number of peaks, it is plausible that the fit could be simplified by reducing one or two peaks through careful adjustment of the fitting parameters. It is important to emphasize that the applicability of Lorentzian decomposition is particularly sensitive at low doses. In these situations, subtle spectral components are difficult to discern, making the fitting optimization algorithm highly susceptible to minute spectral variations.

While radiochromic films are commonly utilized in conjunction with flatbed scanners, this study underscores the advantages of spectroscopic methods for obtaining valuable insights into film dose response. Through relatively straightforward measurements, distinctive spectral signatures were captured for each film type, highlighting their unique characteristics. For EBT3 and EBT4 films, the limit of accurate absorbance measurements exceeded the dynamic range specified by the manufacturer. Conversely, for EBT-XD, this limit fell below the stated maximum dose of 40 Gy. This discrepancy may be attributed to the flatbed scanner's ability to integrate over various wavelengths, which potentially enables a wider dynamic range for transmission measurements in the red channel compared to a single-wavelength instrument such as a spectrophotometer. As noted by Devic *et al* (2007), the development of densitometers that utilize multiple wavelengths for film readout could substantially enhance the accuracy and precision of radiochromic film dosimetry. This study identifies several key factors that could guide the design of such instruments. These include tailoring the device to specific film models to accommodate their unique properties, carefully

selecting wavelengths to optimize readout for each film type, and addressing saturation effects to ensure accurate measurements across the entire dose range. Furthermore, considering polarization sensitivity could additionally improve measurement reliability. The findings in this study establish a strong foundation for the development of advanced instruments for radiochromic film dosimetry, incorporating these key aspects.

A limitation of this study is that the presented results apply exclusively to clinical megavoltage photon and electron beams. Darafsheh *et al* (2020) compared the absorption spectra for photon and proton irradiation, observing a 5% difference in response. Thereby, extrapolating the reported findings to lower energy photon/electron beams, as well as high-linear energy transfer particles such as protons, neutrons, alpha particles, and heavy ions, would be inaccurate due to the non-homogeneous distribution of polymerization centers within the sensitive layer of the film. This sensitive layer consists of a matrix in which these centers are dispersed at micrometer-scale distances, analogous to the distribution of chia seeds within pudding.

5. Conclusion

This comparative study highlighted the differences in distinctive spectral signatures of EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD films for clinical megavoltage photon and electron beam qualities. The absorption spectra can be characterized with nine, eleven, and twelve constituent profiles for EBT3, EBT4, and EBT-XD, respectively. EBT4 spectra indicated a marked improvement in sensitivity and decreased orientation dependence relative

to EBT3 films. EBT-XD exhibited the lowest sensitivity to orientation effects due to polarization, followed by EBT4 and EBT3. The results presented offer an empirical foundation for analyzing and designing novel instruments for radiochromic film readout.

Data availability statement

The data cannot be made publicly available upon publication because no suitable repository exists for hosting data in this field of study. The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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Appendix

Table 1. Average peak positions \bar{x}_i in nanometers for three studied radiochromic films (equation (5)).

Peak ID	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
EBT3	455	501	521	542	560	583	620	633	643	/	/	/
EBT4	401	429	468	504	521	542	561	583	621	633	641	/
EBT-XD	409	431	456	486	502	521	540	562	583	620	632	639

(a) *EBT3 Saturation*

(b) *EBT4 Saturation*

(c) *EBT-XD Saturation*

Figure 7. Saturation of the primary 635 nm peak.

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